
FORMING THE ABILITY TO USE THE DICTIONARY IN THE PROCESS OF ONLINE EDUCATION

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Annotation: Learning vocabulary is a basic constituent of learning a language. Because of the importance of vocabulary to the four macro skills as well as to our study and life, much attention has been paid and many studies have been conducted to investigate effective dictionary learning strategies. Solutions to the problems and suggestions to improve the process of teaching and learning vocabulary were then presented, followed by implications for further research into effective vocabulary learning and dictionary teaching strategies in online teaching English.

Key Terms – vocabulary, dictionary skill, taxonomy, strategy, dictionary learning strategies, using notebooks, lexical piece.

Vocabulary which is generally and widely considered to be one of the most essential elements of a language plays a pivotal role in determining whether or not students will be successful in learning a language and getting their message across. The extensive knowledge of vocabulary is absolutely crucial and highly desirable. It is believed that vocabulary knowledge is vitally important for the four macro skills, such as listening, reading, speaking and writing. Because of the significance of vocabulary knowledge in effective communication, vocabulary learning and instruction are attracting considerable attention from researchers and practitioners, particularly students and teachers. There are a lot of research that has been carried out in the area of dictionary learning strategies in order to determine the effective and most frequently used dictionary learning strategies. Moreover,

many students may not be aware of those crucial strategies and most teachers tend not to teach their students explicitly how to apply dictionary learning strategies as effectively as possible.

Dictionary, which is one of the most important elements of common and general language, plays a crucial role in determining whether students succeed in learning a language and conveying their messages. Extensive knowledge of dictionary is very important and much needed. Vocabulary knowledge is believed to be vital for the four macro skills, such as listening, reading, speaking, and writing. Our lack of vocabulary knowledge can lead to great difficulties in expressing ourselves orally and in writing. Because of the importance of vocabulary knowledge in effective communication, vocabulary learning and teaching are of great importance to researchers and practitioners in identifying effective and most widely used dictionary learning strategies.

General Dictionary Learning Strategies Large-scale research on vocabulary learning strategies has been conducted to identify effective strategies for vocabulary learning. Most of the research focuses on three important areas:

- 1) general vocabulary learning strategies;
- 2) taxonomy of dictionary study strategies;
- 3) strategies for studying the most widely used vocabulary (Lip, 2009; Nation, 2001; Oxford, 1990; Schmitt, 1997).

Dictionary learning strategies typically include cognitive strategies, metacognitive strategies, and social strategies. According to Hedge (2000), students use a range of cognitive strategies to learn words, such as using keywords, creating associations, and learning words in a group. He defines cognition as a mental operation associated with working on new words to understand, classify, and store them in a mental lexicon. Similarly, Schmitt (1997) argues that cognitive strategies, including written and oral repetition, word lists, and flash cards, are common strategies used in many parts of the world.

Taking notes in class and keeping a dictionary is helpful and has been recommended by many teachers and writers. Metacognitive strategies, according to Schmitt (1997, p. 216), are “used by students to monitor and evaluate their own knowledge by providing an overview of the overall learning process”. Social cognitive strategies usually involve asking teachers and peers for synonyms, definitions, or example sentences of a particular unfamiliar word. According to Ghanal (2007), it is important to teach students to be independent in the process of learning the L2 dictionary. Furthermore, in their articles, Hunt and Beglar (2004) emphasize teachers' ability to guess from context by focusing on the value of good sentence examples that provide compound, grammatical, and pragmatic information about words. They emphasize that it is necessary. . They emphasize that dictionary learning strategies, in particular extensive reading and listening, contextual guessing, and vocabulary use, play a major role in developing students' vocabulary knowledge.

In addition, a number of studies have been conducted to study the most commonly used dictionary learning strategies. In a study of Chinese EFL university students in Hong Kong, Lip (2009, p. 77) “discovered the most commonly used and most useful dictionary learning strategies.

- 1) writing the word over and over in the mind;
- 2) word analysis by separating parts of sound;
- 3) memorize words by completing a project;
- 4) Ask classmates what the word means. ”

The three categories are metacognitive strategies, cognitive strategies, and social / affective strategies. They include selective attention, preparation, self-management, repetition, recording, description, and translation among the most commonly used dictionary learning strategies, social / affective strategies (e.g., collaboration) and questionnaire for explanation) are rarely used.

Difficulties in learning and teaching dictionary. The abundance of words in English is a big problem for students and teachers. In addition, the use of text types

that students can read without any difficulty is limited. The same authors also noted the negative impact of dictionary size on English teaching methods. They point out that teachers cannot expect much from their students because of the “size of their English vocabulary”. Nation (2005, p. 47) also states that “the main problem of dictionary teaching is that a small part of what is needed to know a few words and phrases can be solved at the same time” . Many students found that they had problems with “word choice”. In other words, students have difficulty expressing their thoughts in words, i.e., they cannot find the English words needed to express their thoughts in speech and writing. Research has shown that students also face great difficulties in spelling, pronunciation, and understanding of words. He suggested that three goals should be achieved to help students succeed in increasing dictionary and learning:

- 1) focusing on the dictionary,
- 2) searching the dictionary multiple times,
- 1) 3) finding strategies for successful dictionary learning.

In addition to the problems faced by students, teachers also faced a number of challenges in teaching vocabulary to their students. This is not surprising, as problems are rare in the process of learning and teaching dictionary. However, most of the problems reported by teachers were closely related to the challenges students were struggling with. Problems can arise as a result of students' fear or insecurity about taking risks or making mistakes, and to some extent not using the dictionary in class. In other words, students' shyness or unwillingness to participate or be active in the classroom, along with the students' lack of vocabulary, poses a major challenge to a simple vocabulary teaching course. Interestingly, the most common problem teachers have in teaching students dictionary is that if students are unable to spell or pronounce words correctly, students may be shy, o. There were problems with students' inability to use words effectively.

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